

Forecasting of Gas Production and Its Potential Development under the Economic Restrictions: Case Study of Russian Company

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 14, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Forecasting, Gas and Oil Industry, Production, Economic Restrictions, Potential Development, Econometric Model</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4763281</p>	<p><i>This paper presents the essence and functional purpose of economic and social results' forecasting in the gas and oil industry. Authors discuss correlation between production efficiency and market demand in the national and global economy. Methodology: This study uses the econometric model to devote the forecasting of the Russian Gazprom natural gas production in the context of the Russian economic crises and foreign economic restrictions that has taken place since 2014, including a reduction in external and domestic demand for Russian natural gas. On the basis of gas production function estimated for 1999–2020 authors make forecasts for 2021 of Gazprom gas production in Siberia (where the company is producing more than 90% of its gas) and estimate the underutilized production potential of Gazprom company in this region for 2021. Results: It is concluded that in the Russian economic crisis that has been intensified since 2014 as well as the foreign economic and political restrictions that have been started in the same year, the segment of gas production Russian Gazprom continues to be an effective natural monopoly with an increasing coefficient of neutral technical progress, declining average gas production cost in new fields and minimal production costs, the marginal and average values of which coincide and do not depend on the volumes of gas produced.</i></p>

Introduction

The totality of industries engaged in the extraction, transportation and processing of various types of fossil fuels, as well as the production, transformation and distribution of various types of energy (thermal, electrical, etc.), is called the fuel and energy complex (FEC). The fuel and energy complex include the fuel (oil, gas and coal), oil refining, petrochemical and energy (heat, hydro and nuclear) industries.

The fuel and energy complex are the backbone of the modern world economy. The level of development of the fuel and energy complex reflects the social, scientific and technological progress in the country. Indeed, it is difficult to imagine human life without fuel, energy, light, heat, communications, radio, television, transport and household appliances, etc. The development of cybernetics, automation equipment, computing and space technology is impossible without energy. Naturally, therefore, the consumption of energy and, accordingly, energy resources has continuously increased and especially rapidly in the XX century [1].

Analyzing the diagrams and forecast of Shell Corporation until 2050 [2], it can be noted that the share of coal in the global energy balance will gradually decrease, and the demand for natural gas will only increase. The share of renewable energy sources will also grow significantly. The share of oil will slightly decrease and by 2040 may fall to 27%, although the share of oil in the world energy balance will remain the largest. It is worth noting the tendency for an increase in energy demand, so in 1970 the total energy consumption was 4876 million tones. (tone of oil equivalent), and in 2020 already 14,304 million tones; and it will only increase over time. In general, most of the demand for energy in the future, as well as in the past, will be met by minerals.

Figure 1 below shows the latest statistics from British Petroleum on recoverable world oil and coal reserves and production, and the latest OPEC statistics on world recoverable reserves and gas production volumes.

Fig. 1. World gas production statistics, 2010-2018

Source: BP Statistical Review of World Energy, 2019 [3]

For many years, the high level of oil production and its export ensured the growth of the country's economy. However, oil production cannot contribute to the effective development of the economy. More developed countries prefer refining because the sale of high-quality fuels is more profitable than the sale of crude oil. At present, Russia lags behind Western countries in terms of the depth of oil refining. Thus, the depth of oil refining in the USA is about 97%, and in Western Europe - 95%, while in Russia the actual refining depth is about 79% [4]. The low refining depth is associated with the lack of modern deep oil refining processes.

Thus, for at least the next few decades, oil and gas will remain the main energy sources in the world. Russia has large reserves of oil and gas, as well as unconventional oils such as heavy oils, bitumen and shale oils, which help ensure the country's energy security and a good economy. To fully realize the country's oil and gas potential, it is necessary to improve oil refining processes. Creation of new and modernization of existing oil refining capacities will make the oil industry resistant to hydrocarbon feedstock deteriorating in composition and properties. The introduction of modern oil refining processes will make it possible to obtain high quality motor fuels and lubricating oils, which will bring much more benefit to the economy than the production and export of hydrocarbons [5].

The main task of this survey is to investigate the trends of gas and oil production in Russia and its consumption during foreign sanctions.

1. Theory and formula

In the process of forecasting economic results and the effectiveness of economic entities, medium-term estimates obtained by economic and mathematical methods in the presence of a representative sample (a dynamic series of economic indicators), as well as expert methods in the absence of data on the retrospective economic activity of the forecasting object, are necessary for establishing medium-term quantitative values of economic results and the effectiveness of the resource in confidence intervals and threshold values of economic security of a prospective period of time [6].

The established confidence intervals of the values of the indicators of economic results, the effectiveness of the resources used, as the characteristics of the stability of the state of economic security of the management object, are those limitations of their achievement that take into account the most probable deviations from the projected estimates, expressed by the approximation coefficient, depending on the changed trends economic and innovative development under the influence of negative factors of external and internal environments.

The views of a number of economist scholars on the advisability of determining the main performance characteristics in the medium- and long-term socio-economic development of economic entities and the national economy sectors, which are closely correlated with economic security through expert extrapolation of retrospective activity based on observance of the principle of growth of economic results and the effectiveness of the resources used from the previously achieved level, in our opinion, cannot be acceptable neither economically, nor by the adequacy of the established target orientation to achieve the maximum possible values

of economic indicators. This is due to the fact that, in the context of significant changes in the state of the external environment in the medium term, the observance of trends in the growth of economic performance and production efficiency does not allow to establish adequately the level of planned economic security for the established composition of economic indicators. In turn, this can lead to a complete loss of the properties and significance inherent in the functions of forecasting and long-range planning [7].

However, giving the forecasting function only one of the properties of its functional purpose, in our opinion, cannot serve as a preliminary assessment of the achievement in the medium- and long-term periods of the greatest economic, social results, efficiency, the level of conformity of the stability of economic security in the conditions of the unchanged economic and innovative state of external and internal environments. This statement is based on the fact that the functional purpose of forecasting is peculiar not only to establish the adequacy of the balances of balance resources allocated to achieving economic, social results, the effectiveness of the resources used, but also to interact with other management functions, as well as the definition of significant, statistically acceptable assessments of economic security of the activities of organizations and sectoral components of the national economy [8-10].

In this regard, it should be noted that the definition of adequate medium-term forecast values of economic results and resource-consumption costs for business entities and sectoral components of the economy is an acceptable quantitative benchmark for establishing the dynamics of their development and economic security, which, in the medium term, being exposed to economic and innovative influences of factors of unstable external and internal environments.

In 2014, the economy of our country faced foreign economic restrictions, trade and financial, from a number of foreign partners and counterparties. The Russian oil and gas complex did not bypass these restrictions either. Although the main burden of sanctions fell on the Russian oil industry, their consequences seriously affected the domestic gas industry, including Gazprom Company [11]. The negative effect of the sanctions was intensified by the decline in world prices, first for crude oil, and then for natural gas. The consequence of all this has been a reduction in domestic and external demand for Russian gas since 2014, including gas from Gazprom Company. One of the reasons for the decline in demand was the cessation of gas supplies to the east European market. Some of the countries were unable to pay for Russian natural gas, as a result of which gas supplies were practically stopped. Another reason for the decline in gas demand was the general situation in the Russian economy, which since 2014 has been complicated by external economic sanctions. One more reason for the decrease in demand was a decrease in external demand for Russian gas from a number of European countries due to the unfavorable economic situation in their countries and the temperature factor [12-13].

The decrease in demand for Russian gas had a negative impact on the volumes of its production, which began to decline since 2014. Despite this, Russian Gazprom Company continues to increase its production capacity, including at the recently commissioned (2012) large field in Siberia [14].

Thus, the author considers it relevant to forecast natural gas production. Gazprom company and its production potential in the context of external economic constraints. Moreover, in itself, economic and mathematical modeling and forecasting of natural gas production is an important and timely task both for the Russian state and for gas producers and consumers. From the volume of production and sales of natural gas the forecast parameters of the revenues of the state budget of Russia largely depend (including from the mineral extraction tax, MET), export foreign exchange earnings and exchange rates, inflation rates. For gas producers, econometric models of production functions can be useful in predicting the results of the implementation of various production capital investment programs and future profits. For Russian and foreign gas consumers, production forecasting can help in developing a strategy for effective economic solutions depending on the forecasted volumes of gas supplied to the market.

Natural gas production can be predicted using various methods, techniques and models (direct counting, geological and engineering models, logistic curves [15], among which econometric models have a number of significant advantages.

- First, a small number of factors (usually two or three) are sufficient to adequately describe and predict natural gas production.
- Secondly, with the help of one equation it is possible to adequately simulate and fairly accurately predict gas production not only from an individual field, but also from the totality of all deposits of a company, region or country.
- Third, the stability or instability over time of the econometric estimates of the model's production functions allow us to draw important economic conclusions: for example, about the presence or absence of structural changes, about the stability or instability of economic and institutional arrangements, on the sustainability or instability of the objectives of the strategic development of the investigated object.
- Fourth, the experience of econometric analysis shows that it is possible to find production functions in which, over a significant number of years, not only ex-post forecast errors are quite

small, but also the ex-post dynamics of forecast production corresponds to the actual dynamics.

Econometric models of production functions of the gas and oil industry, developed and used in some papers [16-18], and their modifications have already been applied by the author to the study (modeling and forecasting) of new objects [19-20], including number of natural gas production by Gazprom Company from the fields of Siberia.

Afanasyev in 2014 and 2020 [21-22] the author investigated econometric models of production functions of natural gas production at Gazprom Company (excluding Gazprom Company Neft) from the fields of Siberia, where the concern produces more than 90% of natural gas, and on their based on the selection of those functions that most accurately predict production from the point of view of the principle of retrospective calculations (ex-post forecast).

2. Experimental setup

The production function that adequately describes the process of natural gas production from the point of view of economic meaning and classical criteria of econometrics and most accurately predicts the gas production of Gazprom is the exponential function with variable elasticity of fixed assets, studied in the time intervals 1999–2008:

$$P_t = e^{a_0} C_{t-1}^{a_1} G_{1963, t-2}^{a_2} \quad (1)$$

where P_t is the gross production of natural gas in the year t , C_t (1999) is the average annual cost of the main industrial production assets of the main activity (in comparable prices 1999) in year t ; $G_{1963, t-2}$ is the cumulative production of natural gas from the year the industrial production (1963) by year $(t-1)$, where t is time (year).

Table 1. The results of an econometric study of exponential production functions of natural gas production by Gazprom Company in Siberia by the method of least squares in time intervals 1999-2020.

Years	Coefficients and t-statistic			R ²	DW	Ex-post forecast error APE, %	
	a ₀	a ₁	a ₂			Maximum	Average
1999-2003	4,61 (4)	0,56 (6)	-5,12×10 ⁻⁹ (-2,04)	0,99	1,52	4,5	1,8
1999-2004	4,71 (6)	0,55 (10)	-4,89×10 ⁻⁹ (-4)	0,99	1,49	8,4	3,4
1999-2005	4,43 (8)	0,57 (15)	-5,48×10 ⁻⁹ (-6)	0,99	1,57	4,3	1,9
1999-2006	4,60 (10)	0,56 (18)	-5,15×10 ⁻⁹ (-8)	0,99	1,68	4,0	1,8
1999-2007	4,65 (13)	0,56 (23)	-5,07×10 ⁻⁹ (-11)	0,99	1,67	5,1	2,4
1999-2008	4,90 (14)	0,54 (22)	-4,65×10 ⁻⁹ (-11)	0,99	1,57	11,3	5,6
1999-2009	4,60 (11)	0,56 (21)	-5,14×10 ⁻⁹ (-12)	0,99	2,09	4,4	2,0
1999-2010	4,65 (13)	0,56 (22)	-5,05×10 ⁻⁹ (-14)	0,99	2,47	5,5	2,6
1999-2011	4,71 (14)	0,55 (24)	-4,97×10 ⁻⁹ (-16)	0,99	2,41	6,7	3,4
1999-2012	4,72 (15)	0,55 (26)	-4,95×10 ⁻⁹ (-18)	0,99	2,42	6,8	3,8
1999-2013	4,67 (16)	0,55 (28)	-5,02×10 ⁻⁹ (-20)	0,99	2,40	6,0	3,5
1999-2014	4,61 (16)	0,56 (28)	-5,10×10 ⁻⁹ (-21)	0,99	2,25	5,0	3,0
1999-2015	4,59 (16)	0,56 (29)	-5,14×10 ⁻⁹ (-23)	0,99	2,20	4,5	2,8
1999-2016	4,57 (16)	0,56 (29)	-5,19×10 ⁻⁹ (-23)	0,98	2,09	3,9	2,4
1999-2017	4,55 (15)	0,56	-5,24×10 ⁻⁹	0,98	1,84	2,9	1,8

		(28)	(-23)				
1999-2018	4,54 (15)	0,56 (28)	$-5,28 \times 10^{-9}$ (-23)	0,98	1,73	2,4	1,6
1999-2019	4,51 (15)	0,57 (29)	$-5,32 \times 10^{-9}$ (-24)	0,98	1,68	2,0	1,5
1999-2020	4,54 (16)	0,56 (29)	$-5,28 \times 10^{-9}$ (-25)	0,98	1,74	2,3	1,8

Note. R^2 - coefficient of determination, DW - Durbin - Watson statistics.

Source: Afanasyev, 2020a [22].

Indeed, firstly, this function has the value of the coefficient of determination R^2 , reflecting the degree of closeness of the statistical relationship between the resulting variable (gas production) and explanatory variables (the average annual value of fixed industrial assets in comparable prices in 1999 and cumulative gas production), very high. Thus, in 1999-2020 the variation in gas production by more than 99% is due to the change in its cumulative production and the average annual value of the main industrial and production assets in comparable prices in 1999.

Second, the values of the Durbin - Watson statistic indicate that there is no autocorrelation of first-order residuals at the 1% significance level.

Thirdly, t-statistics of estimates of production functions coefficients that are superior show that all considering factors of production are statistically significant. The signs at their coefficients correspond to the existing theoretical and applied concepts. Indeed, the negative coefficient at cumulative production α_2 confirms the fact that as the cumulative production increases, i.e. with depletion of reserves, production falls, since with a constant volume of fixed assets, with an increase in cumulative production, the pressure in the reservoir and the productivity of gaswells. A positive coefficient for fixed assets α_1 shows that an increase in their volume at a given level of depletion of natural gas reserves production gas increases.

Thus, the high quality of approximation of the econometric model and the results of testing statistical hypotheses do not contradict the fact that the parameter estimates production functions obtained by the least squares method in time between 1985 and 2008 are the exact unbiased estimates from all linear unbiased estimates.

Moreover, the econometric model has a high predictive power: it has rather low errors of ex-post forecast APE, where

$$\text{APE} = (\text{Ex - post predicted production} / \text{actual production}) - 1) \times 100\%, \quad (2)$$

not exceeding 5%. In particular, the exponential production function of natural gas production of Gazprom Company from the fields of Siberia, studied in 1999–2020, has ex-post forecast errors for 1999–2020 do not exceed 4.3%, and the direction of the dynamics of ex-post forecasted production volumes almost everywhere coincides with the direction of the dynamics of actual volumes, which indicates a good predictive power of this function [23].

For 2021 forecasted values of natural gas production volumes of Gazprom in Siberia by function significantly (by 12-17%) (figure 2) exceeded the actual volumes, which indicates a temporary underutilization of the company's production potential; the company missed opportunities in the amount of 50-60 billion cubic meters due to a decrease in demand for gas, including effective demand, from some foreign and domestic consumers.

Fig. 2. Actual volumes of natural gas production and ex-post forecasted (potential) volumes of natural gas production for 1999–2020 and forecast for 2021. Data of Gazprom Company in Siberia.

Source: [24].

Despite this, Gazprom, having significant production potential and being a reliable supplier of natural gas, it can profitably realize its potential by laying new routes to those consumers who need it and are willing to pay for it (figure 3).

Fig. 3. Errors of the ex-post forecast of APE for 1999–2021 natural gas production of Gazprom in Siberia by function studied in the time interval 1999–2021, %

Source: [24].

These routes may be additional branches of the Nord Stream, South Stream gas pipelines, Turkish Stream. The predicted value of the production potential of natural gas of Gazprom for 2021 based on function investigated in 1999–2020, is 416 billion cubic meters (figure 4).

Fig. 4. Natural gas production in Siberia, 2015–2019

Source: <http://www.gazprom.ru/about/production/projects/deposits/bm/> [24].

3. Result discussions

Due to the lack of statistical data on the average annual load of fixed assets in gas production, the authors are unable to give more accurate forecasts. At the same time, an indirect assessment of the effect of reducing demand can be given as follows. Assuming that part of the new fixed assets introduced in 2012–2016, is

temporarily underutilized, the forecasted values of natural gas production volumes of Gazprom from the fields of Siberia, calculated on the basis of function, investigated in 1999–2003, will be closer to their actual values in 2021. The forecast error for upcoming years will not exceed 6.2 %. Forecast of the volume of natural gas production in 2017 by Gazprom Company in Siberia based on function studied in 1999–2003 excluding part of the new fixed assets put into operation in 2012–2016, amounts to 373 billion cubic meters [25].

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, we note that in the context of a temporary decrease in gas demand and the presence of other foreign trade restrictions, Russian Gazprom remains a reliable supplier of blue fuel for both domestic and foreign consumers and partners, ready at any time to promptly and uninterruptedly provide and satisfy current and future, including growing, the needs of their counterparties in natural gas. Moreover, in this difficult period for the Russian economy, the efficiency of the economic activities of Gazprom in natural gas production increased. According to our estimates based on an econometric study in 1999–2006 the production function of gas production, including labor, coefficient of neutral technical progress of subsidiaries of gas production Gazprom company in Siberia in 2014 grew by 12%, in 2015 - by 21%, and in 2016 - by 25% compared to 2013. This company produced and continues to extract natural gas at minimal costs, since in 1999–2016 [25]. Values of labor elasticity of natural gas production are very close to the values of the average share of wages with accruals in the costs of gas production.

In this regard, it is no coincidence that the oldest in the Siberia gas production association Gazprom DN, which has been operating the Siberian oil and gas condensate field, the largest on the Yamal peninsula since 2012 with explored and preliminary estimated gas reserves of 4.9 trillion m, starting out since 2014, there has been a continuous decrease in the unit cost of gas production: thus, in comparison since 2013 in 2014 it has decreased by 2%, in 2015 - by 9%, and in 2016 - by 14% [25]. Thus, it can be argued that in the context of the intensified crisis in the Russian economy in 2014, as well as external economic and foreign policy restrictions that began in the same year, Russian Gazprom continues to remain an effective natural monopoly in the field of gas production with a growing coefficient of neutral technical progress, a decreasing unit cost of gas production at new fields and minimal production costs, the limit and average values of which coincide and do not depend on the volumes of gas produced.

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